

Review Article

Exploring the Impact of Green Tea Extract-Enhanced TiO₂, ZnO Nanocomposite: Insights into Cytotoxicity via MTT Assay, Cell Morphology, and Zebrafish Embryonic Study

Suja Joseph*, Deepak Nallaswamy, Rajeshkumar S., Pradeep Dathan, Nazia Rasheed, Leon Jose, Jose Jacob, Tharani Munuswamy

Saveetha Dental College, Chennai, India

Received: 30 May 2024

Accepted: 4 September 2024

Published online: 31 January 2025

Keywords: green synthesis, green tea extract, TiO₂, ZnO nanocomposite, cell viability, biocompatibility

The present study investigates the biological effects of a green-synthesized Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanocomposite, specifically in the form of TiO₂ and ZnO synthesized using green tea extract. Titanium dioxide and zinc oxide nanocomposite was prepared using green tea extract. MTT assay was done to assess cytotoxicity. Acridine orange staining was done to assess morphologic changes. Cell changes were assessed using inverted phase contrast microscope allowing for qualitative assessment of cell morphology and viability. Zebra fish embryonic toxicology evaluation was also done to evaluate the impact of nanoparticles on embryonic development. Cytotoxicity assessments on MG-63 osteosarcoma cells reveal a concentration-dependent response, with lower concentrations (10-40 µl/ml) minimally impacting cell viability and higher concentrations (80 and 100 µl/ml) inducing significant reduction, suggesting potential for targeted cancer therapies. Morphological analysis and acridine orange staining support these findings, showing the nanocomposite's influence on cell migration and increased viability. Zebrafish embryonic toxicology study indicates concentration-dependent effects on hatching kinetics and viability rates, with a transient delay in hatching and subsequent recovery, emphasizing the dynamic impact on embryonic development. Overall, this research provides valuable insights into the nanocomposite's potential applications and raises considerations for its safety and efficacy in biological systems, calling for further exploration of its therapeutic potential and long-term consequences.

© (2024) Society for Biomaterials & Artificial Organs #20005624

Introduction

Metal oxide nanoparticles, such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO) exhibit distinctive physical and chemical properties attributable to their reduced size compared to their bulk counterparts. These nanoparticles possess high surface area, stability, and biocompatibility, rendering them well-suited for diverse applications within the field of nanomedicine [1,2]. Notably, metal oxide nanoparticles have proven effective in water purification and decontamination due to their elevated removal capacity and selectivity towards heavy metals and organic compounds [3]. In the field of nanomedicine, zinc oxide nanoparticles have demonstrated multifaceted properties including antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and wound healing capabilities [4]. Furthermore, metal oxide nanoparticles like titanium dioxide, zinc oxide, and iron oxides have found utility in

various biomedical applications such as diagnostic agents, drug delivery systems, and medical implants [5]. These nanoparticles boast biocompatibility, low toxicity, and the ability to be efficiently cleared from the human body, underscoring their suitability for diverse biomedical applications.

The eco-friendly production of metal oxide nanoparticles involves the utilization of natural extracts and biological components derived from plants, bacteria, fungi, and other organisms [6,7]. Plant extracts, particularly from leaves, are a popular choice owing to the presence of phytochemicals like flavonoids, terpenoids, and carboxylic acids, which contribute to enhanced bioactivity and nanoparticle compatibility [8]. The green synthesis method employs mild reactions, non-toxic precursors, and results in minimal waste generation, thereby establishing its environmental friendliness [9]. Metal oxide nanoparticles produced through green synthesis exhibit versatile applications in catalysis, medicine, agriculture, and energy sectors. The approach offers benefits such as cost-effectiveness, decreased chemical waste, and precise control

* Corresponding author

E-mail address: sjkt21@gmail.com (Dr. Suja Joseph)

over the size and shape of nanoparticles. Moreover, these nanoparticles can manifest distinctive physical and chemical properties, rendering them suitable for diverse industrial applications [10].

Green tea leaf extract offers numerous health benefits attributed to its rich phytochemical constituents. The presence of polyphenols notably catechins, within the extract has been linked to a range of positive health effects, including antioxidant and antimicrobial activities, along with potential therapeutic properties [11,12]. Beyond polyphenols, green tea extract contains amino acids, carbohydrates, and significant tannins with antioxidant properties, collectively contributing to its overall health-promoting effects [13]. The catechins found in green tea, particularly (-)-epigallocatechin-3-gallate, play a crucial role in the extract's pharmacodynamics, showcasing various beneficial effects [11]. Ongoing research has explored the potential of green tea extract in preventing chronic diseases such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases, as well as its antimetabolic syndrome and antidiabetic properties [14].

The current research aims to assess the cytotoxicity of this nanocomposite on MG-63 osteosarcoma cells to evaluate its potential for targeted cancer therapies. Additionally, the study delves into the nanocomposite's impact on cell morphology and migration detected using acridine orange staining and conducts a zebra fish embryonic toxicology study to understand concentration-dependent effects on hatching and viability rates. The overarching goal is to provide comprehensive insights into the nanocomposite's potential applications, considering safety and efficacy in biological systems, and prompting further exploration of its therapeutic potential and long-term consequences.

Materials and Methods

Green tea was subjected to controlled boiling process to extract the bioactive compounds from it. Boiled and filtered green tea extract was added to titanium (IV) oxide precursor (1.93803.0521 EMPLURA[®] titanium (IV)oxide) and zinc oxide precursor (zinc nitrate hexahydrate extrapure AR, 99%) for preparation of TiO₂ and ZnO nanoparticles. After that the nanoparticles were mixed in a magnetic stirrer to ensure thorough dispersion and homogenization to form a cohesive mass. This was dried in a hot air oven and made into a powdered nanocomposite [15].

The green tea-mediated nanoparticles and nanocomposites were characterized using several techniques: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to examine their morphology, Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) to confirm the elemental composition, and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) to identify the functional groups present in the synthesized material [15].

The SEM image reveals that the TiO₂ nanoparticles are small and exhibit a rhombic shape. The ZnO nanoparticles appeared as small uniformly spherical particles. This observation highlights the effectiveness of the green synthesis in producing nanoparticles with fine dimensions and a distinct morphology. The size of TiO₂ nanoparticles ranges from 50 to 100 nm, while ZnO nanoparticles range from 25 to 50 nm. The small particle size underscores the success of this process in achieving a high level of control over nanoparticles characteristics. The TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposite displayed a combination of rhomboid-shaped and spherical particles, indicating a complex and heterogeneous structure that could influence its properties and applications. This unique structural diversity makes the nanocomposite a promising candidate for various biomedical applications, potentially enhancing its performance and versatility in these fields [15].

The EDX analysis confirms the successful synthesis of the TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposite by revealing the presence of titanium, zinc, and oxygen, indicating the integration of both TiO₂ and ZnO components. Additionally, the notable carbon content suggests residual organic material from the green synthesis process, which could contribute to the nanocomposite's distinctive properties [15].

The FT-IR spectrum of the TiO₂-ZnO nanocomposite reveals peaks corresponding to specific functional groups, including hydroxyl and carbonyl groups. These functional groups play a key role in the synthesis and stabilization of the nanocomposite. The presence of these chemical bonds supports the effective mediation of green tea extract in the formation of the nanocomposite [15].

Cell line maintenance

Osteosarcoma cell line (MG-63) was obtained from the NCCS, Pune. The cells were grown in T25 culture flasks containing Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum) and 1% antibiotics. Cells were maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. Upon reaching confluency, the cells were trypsinized and passaged.

The cell viability (MTT) assay

It is a colorimetric assay for assessing the cell metabolic activity, an indicator of cell viability proliferation and cytotoxicity. The Human Osteosarcoma cell line (MG-63) was plated in 96 well plates with the concentration of 5×10³cells/well in DMEM media with 1X Antibiotic Solution and 10 % fetal bovine serum (Gibco) in CO₂ incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂. The cells were washed with 100µL of 1x PBS(Phosphate Buffered Saline), then the cells were treated with different concentrations (10 to 100 µl/ml) of Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) nanocomposite incubated in CO₂ incubator at 37°C with 5% CO₂ for 24 hours. The medium was aspirated from cells at the end of the treatment period. 0.5mg/mL MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) prepared in 1x PBS was added and incubated at 37°C for 4 hrs using CO₂ incubator. After incubation period, the medium containing MTT was discarded from the cells and washed using 200 µL of PBS. The formed crystals was dissolved with 100 µL of DMSO and thoroughly mixed. The development of color intensity was measured at 570nm. The formazan dye turns purple blue color. The absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader.

The percentage cell viability was measured using the formula: cell viability = [O.D of treated cells/O.D of control cells] × 100.

Cell Morphology

The Osteosarcoma cell line (5x10⁴) were placed in a plate with six wells to study the effect of Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) nanocomposite on cell morphological changes. The cells were treated with and without Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) Nanocomposite (60 µl/ml) for 24 hrs time point. After the treatment period, the cells were washed with PBS and observed in an inverted phase contrast microscope (Labomed TCM-400, USA).

Acridine orange staining

The Osteosarcoma cell line (5x10⁴) were placed in a plate with six wells for live imaging using acridine orange staining. The cells were treated with and without Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) Nanocomposite (60 µl/ml) for 24hrs time point. After incubation period, the cells were washed with PBS and then stained with acridine orange. Stained cells were washed two times with PBS. Stained cells were examined under inverted fluorescence microscope.

Zebra fish embryonic toxicology study

Fish maintenance and Ag NPs exposure

Wild-type zebra fish (*Danio rerio*) were acquired from local Indian vendors and were housed in individual tanks under controlled conditions of temperature ($28.0 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$), light/dark cycle (14:10 h), and pH (6.8–8.5). The fishes were fed with commercially available dry blood worms or optimum food twice a day. Zebra fish embryos were obtained by crossing one female and three males per breeding tank, and viable eggs were collected and rinsed at least three times with freshly prepared E3 medium without methylene blue. The study involved the placement of fertilized eggs in culture plates of varying well sizes (6, 12, and 24 wells) with 20 embryos per 2mL solution per well. The experimental treatment and control groups were replicated three times. To prepare the experimental treatment, a stock suspension of Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) nanocomposite with five different concentrations was freshly made and added directly to the E3 medium. The solution was sonicated for 15 minutes to disperse the nanoparticles while maintaining a pH range of 7.2–7.3. Healthy fertilized embryos were exposed to different concentrations of nanocomposite ranging from (1 μL , 5 μL , 10 μL , 20 μL , and 40 μL) for 0–96 hours post fertilization (hpf). The green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) nanocomposite was added to the E3 medium in which the embryos were incubated. Control groups were also included in the experiment. Dead embryos were removed from the nanoparticles exposed groups every 12 hours. All experimental plates were wrapped in foil to exclude light and maintained at 28°C .

Zebra fish embryo evaluation

Throughout the exposure period following fertilization, the developmental stages of Zebra fish embryos were monitored using a stereo microscope. The embryos were subjected to various concentrations of nanocomposite (1 μL , 5 μL , 10 μL , 20 μL , and 40 μL) for 0–96 hpf. Embryonic mortality and hatching rates were assessed at 24-hour intervals. The study endpoints included embryo/hatchling mortality, hatching rate, and the identification and documentation of any malformations among the embryos and larvae in both control and treatment groups. Photographs of malformed embryos were captured using a COSLAB - Model: HL-10A light microscope, and the percentage of abnormal embryos was recorded every 24 hours.

Results and Discussion

MMT Assay

In this study, the researchers investigated the cytotoxic effects of green tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite at varying concentrations (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$) on MG-63 cells over a 24-hour exposure period (figure 1). The cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay, and the results were reported as means with standard deviations (SD) based on three replicates. Statistical significance was determined using p-values, with asterisks (*) denoting significance when $p < 0.05$. The optical density (O.D) values were used to represent cell viability as a percentage relative to the control group, which was set at 100%.

The data showed that at concentrations of 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, 20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, and 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, the Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite did not significantly alter cell viability compared to the control group, as indicated by non-significant p-values ($p > 0.05$). At these concentrations, cell viability remained relatively close to 100%. However, as the concentration increased to 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, the nanocomposite induced a moderate but non-significant reduction in cell viability ($p = 0.408812$).

Figure 1: The cytotoxic effects of Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite (10–100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$) on MG-63 cells. Cells were treated with Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite (10–100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$) for 24hr and cell viability was evaluated by MTT assay. Data are shown as means \pm SD ($n = 3$). * compared with the control group, $p < 0.05$

The most significant effects were observed at concentrations of 80 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$ and 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, with p-values of 0.014927 and 0.019462, respectively, signifying a substantial decrease in cell viability compared to the control group. At 80 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, cell viability dropped to 91.36578%, and at 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$, it decreased further to 83.83046%. These results suggest that the green tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite exhibits a concentration-dependent cytotoxic effect on MG-63 cells, with a clear dose-response relationship.

Cell morphology

In figure 2, the study focused on the impact of Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite treatment at a concentration of 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$ on human osteoblast-like cells (MG-63) after 24 hours, in comparison to a control group. Cellular changes were visualized using an inverted phase contrast microscope, allowing for the qualitative assessment of cell migration and morphology. The results indicated a noteworthy difference between the nanocomposite-treated group and the control group, particularly in terms of cell migration.

The microscopic images revealed that, following treatment with Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) nanocomposite, the cells exhibited enhanced migration capabilities when compared to the control group. The cells in the treated group displayed characteristics suggestive of increased motility, such as elongated and more spread-out cell morphologies, which are indicative of active cell migration. In contrast, the cells in the control group displayed a comparatively less migratory phenotype. These visual observations are consistent with the notion that the Green Tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) nanocomposite, at the specified concentration (60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$), exerts a stimulating effect on cell migration in MG-63 osteoblast-like cells. The results from figure 2 underscore the relevance of exploring the impact of this nanocomposite on cell behavior, which may have implications for regenerative medicine and tissue engineering applications.

Live Cell Imaging -Acridine Orange staining

In figure 3, the study investigated the impact of green tea ($\text{TiO}_2 + \text{ZnO}$) Nanocomposite treatment at a concentration of 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$ on human osteoblast-like cells (MG-63) after 24 hours, in

Figure 2: Human osteoblast like cells (MG-63) were treated with Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) Nanocomposite (60 il/ml) was performed at 24h along with control group. Images were obtained using an inverted phase contrast microscope

comparison to a control group. Following the treatment, the cells were subsequently subjected to acridine orange staining, and images were captured using an inverted fluorescence microscope. The results revealed a distinct difference between the nanocomposite treated group and the control group, particularly with regard to cell viability and morphology.

The microscopic images obtained after acridine orange staining indicated that, post-treatment with the green tea (TiO₂ + ZnO) Nanocomposite, the treated group exhibited a noticeably higher number of live cells in comparison to the control group. This observation was manifested by an abundance of green-fluorescent cells in the treated group, which corresponded to live and metabolically active cells. In contrast, the control group displayed comparatively fewer green-fluorescent cells, indicating a lower percentage of live cells. These findings suggest that the Green Tea (TiO₂ + ZnO) Nanocomposite, at the specified concentration (60 µl/ml), has a positive impact on cell viability in MG-63 osteoblast-like cells. The results presented in figure 3 emphasize the importance

of a comprehensive assessment of treatment effects and underscore the need for further research to understand the molecular mechanisms responsible for the observed increase in cell survival in osteoblast cells.

Zebra fish embryonic toxicology evaluation

Hatching rate

The hatching kinetics of zebra fish embryos treated with (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite at concentrations of 1 µL, 5 µL, 10 µL, 20 µL, and 40 µL were investigated at post-fertilization time points (0, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hours). The control group exhibited a consistent 100% hatching rate, indicative of normal development. In contrast, treated groups displayed concentration-dependent effects, with a delayed hatching observed at 24 hours, particularly at higher concentrations. However, by 48 hours, all treatment groups demonstrated substantial increases in hatching rates, and by 72 hours, complete hatching was achieved, except for the 40 µL group, which showed a 90% rate. By 96 hours, all concentrations reached a

Figure 3: Human osteoblast like cells (MG-63) were treated with Green Tea (TiO₂ +ZnO) nanocomposite (60 il/ml) was performed at 24h along with control group. After the treatment cells were treated with acridine orange and Images were obtained using an inverted fluorescence microscope

Figure 4: Zebra fish embryos treated with green tea extract mediated (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite

Figure 6: Viability rate of green synthesized (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite

Figure 5: Hatching rate of green tea extract mediated (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite

100% hatching rate, comparable to the control. These findings suggest a transient impact of (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite exposure on zebra fish embryonic hatching kinetics, with recovery to normal levels over time.

Viability rate

The viability rates of zebra fish embryos exposed to (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite concentrations (1 μL, 5 μL, 10 μL, 20 μL, and 40 μL) were assessed at different post-fertilization time points (0, 24, 48, 72, and 96 hours) compared to the control group. The control embryos consistently exhibited a 100% viability rate throughout the experiment, indicating normal development. In the treated groups, initial viability rates were unaffected at 24 hours, but a concentration-dependent decline was observed at 48 hours, with the 20 μL and 40 μL groups showing 80% and 70% viability, respectively. This trend continued at 72 hours, with the 20 μL and 40 μL groups further decreasing to 75% and 70%, and at 96 hours,

reaching 90%, 70%, and 65% viability for the 10 μL, 20 μL, and 40 μL groups, respectively. The findings suggest a concentration-dependent impact of (TiO₂ + ZnO) nanocomposite on zebra fish embryo viability, highlighting the importance of understanding the underlying mechanisms and potential long-term consequences on embryonic development.

Discussion

The results of the study provide a comprehensive understanding of the biological effects of the green-synthesized Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles, particularly in the form of a TiO₂ + ZnO nanocomposite. The cytotoxicity assessment on MG-63 osteosarcoma cells demonstrated a concentration-dependent response, with lower concentrations (10-40 μl/ml) having minimal impact on cell viability, while higher concentrations (80 and 100 μl/ml) induced a significant reduction. This dose-response relationship suggests a potential application of the nanocomposite in targeted cancer therapies. Morphological analysis and acridine orange staining further supported these findings, revealing that the nanocomposite induced changes in cell migration and increased cell viability, emphasizing its potential as a modulator of cellular behaviour. The microscopic images of treated cells exhibited enhanced migration capabilities, and acridine orange staining demonstrated a higher number of live cells post-treatment.

Green tea-synthesized nanoparticles (GT-ZVI NPs) have demonstrated selective cytotoxic effects on tumoral cells, particularly human chondrosarcoma cells, while exhibiting lower toxicity towards normal cells [16]. In a similar trend, silver nanoparticles synthesized using white tea extract (Wt/Ag-NPs) displayed dose-dependent cytotoxicity against MOLT-4 cancer cells [17]. Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) synthesized in conjunction with graphene oxide (GO) nanosheets (ZnO/GO NC) exhibited noteworthy anticancer activity against lung cancer cells (A549) and human breast cancer cells (MCF-7) [18]. Selenium nanoparticles derived from Java tea leaves demonstrated cytotoxic effects on L6 rat skeletal muscle cell lines [19]. Moreover, zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized from *Scutellaria baicalensis* root extract exhibited dose-dependent cytotoxic effects on HeLa cells [20]. Collectively, these studies underscore the potential of green tea, white tea, and herbal tea extracts in nanoparticle synthesis with selective cytotoxicity against

cancer cells, suggesting their promising role in cancer treatment strategies.

The zebra fish embryonic toxicology study added another layer to the results, indicating concentration-dependent effects on hatching kinetics and viability rates. While there was a transient delay in hatching at early time points, the embryos eventually exhibited recovery to normal levels, emphasizing the dynamic nature of the nanocomposite's impact on embryonic development. The decline in viability rates over time in zebra fish embryos exposed to higher concentrations further underscores the need for a nuanced understanding of the nanocomposite's long-term consequences on embryonic development.

Zebra fish embryonic toxicology studies have been important in understanding the impact of nanoparticles, including titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO), on embryonic development. Chokkattu et al. conducted an assessment of TiO₂ nanoparticles in dental varnish, revealing significant alterations in deformity rates and hatchability of zebra fish embryos at experimental doses [21]. In a study by Chen et al., the developmental neurobehavioral toxicity of TiO₂ nanoparticles was investigated, unveiling disturbances in motor and social behavior in larval zebra fish, correlated with cell apoptosis and oxidative stress-induced neuronal damage [22]. In contrast, Pecoraro et al. explored the effects of cerium oxide (CeO₂) nanoparticles on zebra fish embryos and found no lethality or sub-lethal impacts on embryonic development. However, an increased expression of 7-Ethoxyresorufin-O-Diethylase (EROD) suggested potential metabolic effects [23]. These studies collectively contribute to a nuanced understanding of the diverse effects of nanoparticles on zebra fish embryonic development, emphasizing the need for tailored investigations into specific nanoparticle types and their potential consequences.

In summary, the results indicate that the green-synthesized TiO₂ + ZnO nanocomposite exhibits concentration-dependent cytotoxic effects on MG-63 cells and transient impacts on zebra fish embryonic development. These findings provide valuable insights into the potential applications of the nanocomposite in cancer therapy and raise important considerations for its safety and efficacy in biological systems.

Conclusion

The comprehensive investigation into the biological effects of the green-synthesized TiO₂ and ZnO nanocomposite offers valuable insights into its potential applications, particularly in targeted cancer therapies. The concentration-dependent cytotoxic effects observed on MG-63 cells suggest a promising avenue for therapeutic interventions. Additionally, the nanocomposite's impact on cellular behaviour, as evidenced by morphological changes and increased cell viability, further supports its potential as a modulator of biological processes. The zebra fish embryonic toxicology study reveals dynamic effects on hatching kinetics and viability rates, emphasizing the need for a nuanced understanding of its consequences on embryonic development. While the transient nature of the observed delays in hatching implies potential for recovery, the decline in viability rates at higher concentrations underscores the importance of considering long-term effects. This research not only sheds light on the nanocomposite's therapeutic potential but also underscores the necessity for continued exploration to ensure its safety and efficacy in diverse biological systems. Future studies should delve deeper into the underlying mechanisms, optimize dosage for therapeutic applications, and address potential long term implications for both cancer therapy and embryonic development.

References

1. Yadav M, Sharma P, Chauhan NS. Metal oxide-based heterostructures for antimicrobial activity. *Metal Oxide-Based Heterostructures*, 535–70(2023).
2. P. Jain, M. Guin, and N. B. Singh. Metal oxide nanoparticles for water decontamination in Nanohybrid Materials for Water Purification, Springer Nature Singapore. 245–278(2022).
3. Sadhasivam S, Shanmugam M, Umamaheswaran PD, Venkattappan A, Shanmugam A. Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles: Green Synthesis and Biomedical Applications. *Journal of Cluster Science*, 32:1441–55(2020).
4. Karthikeyan B, Gnanakumar G, Therasa Alphonsa A. Future is on Cheap Metal Oxides—A Review. *Nano Metal Oxides b*:111–20 (2023)
5. Murthy S, Effiong P, Fei CC. Metal oxide nanoparticles in biomedical applications. *Metal Oxide Powder Technologies*, 233–51(2020).
6. Venkatchalam CD, Sengottian M, Ravichandran SR. Green synthesis of nanoparticles—metals and their oxides. *Nanomaterials*, 79–96(2021).
7. Jeevanandam J, Chan YS, Danquah MK. Biosynthesis of Metal and Metal Oxide Nanoparticles. *Chem Bio Eng Reviews*, 3:55–67(2016).
8. Muthuvinothini A, Stella S. Green synthesis of metal oxide nanoparticles and their catalytic activity for the reduction of aldehydes. *Process Biochemistry*, 77:48–56(2019).
9. Vinitha G. Review on Green Synthesis of Metal Oxide Nanoparticles for Potential Applications. *Research Aspects in Chemical and Materials Sciences*, 1:40–55(2022).
10. Nguyen NHA, Padil VVT, Slaveykova VI, Èerník M, Ševcù A. Green Synthesis of Metal and Metal Oxide Nanoparticles and Their Effect on the Unicellular Alga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. *Nanoscale Research Letters*, 13(2018)
11. Bag S, Mondal A, Majumder A, Banik A. Tea and its phytochemicals: Hidden health benefits & modulation of signalling cascade by phytochemicals. *Food Chemistry*, 371(2022).131098.
12. I. Asik, R. Satarupa, P. Keya Health benefits of green tea: A mini review. *Journal of entomology and zoology studies*, 2020.
13. Khudhur Ahmad Al-Mahdi Z, M.J. Ewadh R, Khazal Kadhim Hindi N. Health Benefits of Aqueous Extract of Black and Green Tea Leaves. *Bioactive Compounds in Nutraceutical and Functional Food for Good Human Health 2021*.
14. Ullah N, Ahmad M, Aslam H, Tahir MA, Aftab M, Bibi N, et al. Green tea phytochemicals as anticancer: A review. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease* 6:330–6(2016).
15. Joseph S, Nallaswamy D, Rajeshkumar S, Dathan P, Ismail S, Rasheed N et al. Preparation and characterisation of Ti O₂ , ZnO based nanocomposite material using green tea extract. *Trends Biomater Artif Organs* , 38(1), 14-22 (2024) .
16. Lourenço IM, Pieretti J C, Nascimento MHM , Lombello CB, Seabra AB. Eco-friendly synthesis of iron nanoparticles by green tea extract and cytotoxicity effects on tumoral and non-tumoral cell lines. *Energy, Ecology and Environment* 4:261–70(2019).
17. Haghparasti Z, Mahdavi Shahri M. Green synthesis of water-soluble nontoxic inorganic polymer nanocomposites containing silver nanoparticles using white tea extract and assessment of their in vitro antioxidant and cytotoxicity activities. *Materials Science and Engineering*, 87:139–48 (2018).
18. Nagaraj E, Shanmugam P, Karuppanan K, Chinnasamy T, Venugopal S. The biosynthesis of agraphene oxide-based zinc oxide nanocomposite using *Dalbergia latifolia* leaf extract and its biological applications. *New Journal of Chemistry*, 44:2166–79(2020).
19. Sivakumar C, Jeganathan K. In-vitro cytotoxicity of java tea mediated selenium nanoballs against L6 cell lines. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 8:195–200 (2018).
20. Tetey CO, Shin HM. Evaluation of the antioxidant and cytotoxic activities of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized using *scutellaria baicalensis* root. *Scientific African* 6:e00157 (2019).
21. Chokkattu JJ, Mary DJ, Shanmugam R, Neeharika S. Embryonic Toxicology Evaluation of Ginger- and Clove-mediated Titanium Oxide Nanoparticles-based Dental Varnish with Zebrafish. *The Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*, 23:1157–62(2023).
22. Chen J, Lei L, Mo W, Dong H, Li J, Bai C, et al. Developmental titanium dioxide nanoparticle exposure induces oxidative stress and neurobehavioral changes in zebrafish. *Aquatic Toxicology*, 240(2021)
23. Torres-Ruiz M, De La Vieja A, De Alba Gonzalez M, Esteban Lopez M, Castaño Calvo A, Cañas Portilla AL. Toxicity of nanoplastics for zebrafish embryos, what we know and where to go next. *Science of the Total Environment*, 2021;797(2021).